
Deliverable D-JIP2-1.5: Annual meeting Workpackage 1

Responsible Partner: RIVM

Contributing partners: Bfr, APHA, IZS,
AM, CVI, SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D-JIP2-1.5 Annual meeting
WP and Task	JIP-WP1 Task 1.5 Annual meeting for all partners to discuss general project issues and to share and discuss progression in the WP's
Leader	Kitty Maassen
Other contributors	RIVM, Bfr, APHA, IZS-AM, WBVR, SVA
Due month of the deliverable	26
Actual submission month	35
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	OTHER: Meeting
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PUBLIC

Summary Online Annual Meeting November 24 & 26 2020

WPs, tasks & leaders:	Email-address
WP2 Integrated risk-analysis at the national level (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)	kitty.maassen@rivm.nl
2.1 Implementation guidelines for One Health Risk Analysis Structures (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)	kitty.maassen@rivm.nl
2.2 Decision tool to support One Health Risk Assessment (Charlotte Cook, APHA)	charlotte.cook@apha.gov.uk
2.3 Pilots of implementation guidelines for One Health Risk Analysis Structures (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)	kitty.maassen@rivm.nl
WP3 Towards an EU zoonoses structure (Elina Lahti, SVA)	elina.lahti@sva.se
3.1 Exchange of early signals of zoonotic events within and between countries in Europe – barriers and facilitating factors (Maria Nöremark, SVA)	maria.noremark@sva.se
3.2 Select tools for Horizon scanning and signal detection (Rickard Knutsson, SVA)	rickard.knutsson@sva.se
3.3 Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks (Charlotte Cook, APHA)	charlotte.cook@apha.gov.uk
3.4 Pilots One Health early warning system (Charlotte Cook, APHA)	charlotte.cook@apha.gov.uk
3.5 Development of tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis (Charlotte Cook, APHA)	charlotte.cook@apha.gov.uk
WP4 Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control (Adriano Di Pasquale, IZS-AM)	a.dipasquale@izs.it
4.1 Molecular typing data and metadata – database implementation (Adriano Di Pasquale, IZS-AM)	c.camma@izs.it
4.2 Development of a platform-independent tracing framework (Marion Gottschald, BfR)	Marion.Gottschald@bfr.bund.de
4.3 Development of a platform-independent risk modeling framework (Christin Wallstab, BfR)	Christin.wallstab@bfr.bund.de
4.4 Dissemination (Marion Gottschald)	Marion.Gottschald@bfr.bund.de

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Day 1. November 24 2020

Day 2. November 26, 2020

Day 1. November 24, 2020

1. WP 3.1: Exchange of early signals of zoonotic events within and between countries in Europe – barriers and facilitating factors

Maria Nöremark (SVA) - Contact: maria.noremark@sva.se

Acknowledge the importance of personal contacts

Ensure that there are occasions when people can meet in person to learn to know each other, ensure that new colleagues are included. There should be regular meetings. Interviewees gave examples of benefits of annual meetings in person, as well as short telephone conferences once a week. Also, collaboration projects across sectors, across regions and on international level are beneficial.

Structures in place, and understanding for each other's roles and mandates

Along with personal contacts, clear structures (e.g. procedures, routines, legislation) for signal sharing within and between sectors are vital for signal sharing.

Make sure that the involved actors understand each other's roles and mandates (e.g. mandates to take control-actions) and understand the epidemiological situation in other sectors.

Failor to understand these can lead to e.g. expectations of a sector to act beyond their mandate, or overreaction on early signals from another sector.

Strive for well-functioning cross sectional technical systems, make it possible to share and access data

Strive for cross sectional and cross regional technical systems, or at least systems communicating with each other. Ensure that relevant data can be shared within and between sectors, and between countries. Relevant data could be a subset of accessible data, without being in conflict with e.g. GDPR legislation.

Make sure that relevant actors and persons have access to relevant data, an example could be to ensure that regions have access to data from neighbouring regions.

2. EFSA: EC mandate on One Health system for the collection and analysis of WGS data from food/animal isolates

Valentina Rizzi (EFSA) – Contact: valentina.rizzi@efsa.europa.eu

A **centralized WGS data collection** is needed to support promptly the investigation of multi-country foodborne outbreaks

In the design of the centralized data collection and analysis system many **key factors** should be considered, keeping the balance between openness/ transparency versus data ownership/ confidentiality/ engagement

Dialogue with all stakeholders is crucial

3. WP 4.1 A: Status of the COHESIVE information system and the Feasibility Study WP

Adriano Di Pasquale (IZS) – Contact: a.dipasquale@izs.it

Task 4.1 Steps of the feasibility study at MS level

1. Choice of pathogen species
2. List of the involved organizations
3. List of all the useful information sources,
4. A prototype system is used to let the Member State evaluate the expected improvements:
 - a) Evaluate integration of the systems
 - b) Evaluate the possibility to provide EU harmonized output

4. WP4.1 B: Data Harmonization: SIGMA-EST perspective

Paolo Calistri (IZS) – Contact: p.calistri@izs.it

SIGMA project

- Current data collection from MS is not efficient
- The main objective of the project is to provide EFSA with all necessary technical support in developing and implementing an automatized data collection and reporting system on:
 - animal populations
 - surveillance of animal diseases (LSD , AI, ASF)

SIGMA EST

- SIGMA EST (Extract and STandardise) aims at satisfying the requirement of data exchange among Information systems speaking different «languages» in terms of Catalogues and Codes.
- The main characteristics of the application are:
 - make minimum impact for the involved actors
 - maximum flexibility in the configuration
 - very intuitive user interface
- SIGMA EST will serve as a 'simultaneous translator' adapting the original file to the 'language' of the recipients, thanks to the work of analysis of data and dictionaries in use in MSs previously carried out.
- SIGMA EST is a reversible mapping service which will be able to recognise the codes/syntax used by the MSs and translate them into the standard EFSA's dictionary.
- MSs can download the data from the EFSA's database with an automatic re codification according to the codes used at national level .

Catalogue Mapping

Catalogue Mapping is the definition of relationships between the country's catalogues and SIGMA catalogues, within the corresponding attributes:

- SIMPLE Mapping: perfect correspondence between one value of the country's catalogue and the corresponding SIGMA catalogues.
- COMPLEX Mapping: Country has to associate for one value of its catalogue more than one value of SIGMA catalogues, one for each attribute associated in Semantic mapping
- MULTIPLE Mapping: Country has to associate more than one value of its Catalogues to one value of SIGMA catalogue

5. 4.2: Development of a platform-independent tracing framework - current status and outlook

Marion Gottschald (BFR) - Contact: foodrisklabs@bfr.bund.de

Results subtask 4.2.1

- Report – [Deliverable: June 2019, submitted]
- Comparison of tools available: <http://socialcompare.com/en/comparison/tracing-tools-for-supply-chains-4lh89xq0> → check and add
- FCL is the only available tool for “supply chain tracing” applications for authorities
- All other tools are commercial and have a different focus: managing processes of food business companies
- None of the tools includes WGS data in their analysis
- Some functionalities of commercial tools potentially useful for web-based tracing platform (e.g. food ingredient database, barcode reader)

Results subtask 4.2.2

- Restricted area designed and developed
- Legal framework set up
- Data model for data collection form
- Data exchange interfaces defined and implemented
- First analyses and visualizations realized and performance needs identified

- New reporting templates implemented
- FCL Web in production → <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin>

First achievements and results subtask 4.2.3

- Meeting with German public health authority (RKI). Data is needed + Cooperation
- FCL reporting module shows case and sample information
- NOVA model to predict suspicious food items from distribution of cases and whole sales data in progress
- ➔ Final steps: Data collection interface, WGS interface and NOVA prediction model.

Integrative activities & impact

- EFSA, cooperation on
 - Establishment of data standards for supply chain tracing
 - Establishment of standards for ROA reports → results from FCL tracing web portal available via RASFF notifications
 - EU-wide Workshops on tracing
 - EU-wide foodborne outbreak investigation team
- ECDC
 - Joint workshops on foodborne outbreaks together with EFSA and selected member states
- NOVA & COHESIVE partners
- FCL part of Tripartite Tool Box (SISOT)
- Dissemination!
 - MS use FCL more often (UK, AT, HU, PL, ES)
 - FCL team more often requested in Germany + by MS

Possibilities to contribute

- Sharing tracing data
- Promising tools or features

6. WP 4.3: Current project status of the development of Web App for quantitative risk assessment

Thomas Selhorst (BfR) – Contact: Thomas.Selhorst@bfr.bund.de

Powerful and flexible risk modelling tools needed

- Commercial solutions – licensing may be an obstacle, sometimes transparency issues
- Online solutions – pre-specified models not flexible enough
- External solutions – not suitable to implement own developments
- BfR created a risk modelling environment using R as basis for further developments

To do's 2020

- Implementation of Stratification
- Validation
- Processing of user feedback

Day 2. November 26, 2020

1. WP 3.3: Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks

Rob Dewar (APHA) – Contact: Robert.Dewar@apha.gov.uk; Charlotte.Cook@apha.gov.uk

Initial findings Q-fever reporting structure

- Post mortem by APHA affiliated vets is regular but not guaranteed.
- If they go through APHA, Q-fever will likely be found in a suspected case.
- However it is just as valid that farmers would choose commercial testing (as it may be cheaper).
- These often only test for veterinary notifiable diseases, and Q-fever is missed.\

- And even if these labs find Q-fever, there is no pooled data registry to compile these results.
- So this represents a major gap.
- Would be curious to know whether similar issues are face elsewhere!

Plans for the future

- Try to find out how many cases are likely to be missed.
- Identify some recommendations to fill these gaps.

2. WP 3.4: Pilots One Health early warning system

Rob Dewar (APHA) - Contact: Robert.Dewar@apha.gov.uk; Charlotte.Cook@apha.gov.uk

The plan

- Want to stage a One Health signal sharing workshop
- People from different backgrounds can join and share low level trends
- Can meet, discuss and make lasting contacts across borders
- Subvert some of the barriers to signal sharing.
- Participants will be active and passive.
- Active participants will present one or two interesting trends from their country.
- Others will join in discussions following each presentation, to see if they can add to that topic, and gain a deeper understanding of low level issues in other countries.

The meeting

- Will take 3 hours
- Sometime in early 2021
- The presentations last 15 minutes (maximum)
- Content can be anything One Health related and low level, preferably related to a disease or recent epidemiological trend
- An example could be something as simple as a translation of a national zoonoses report

Contributions

- We would like contributions from consortium members
- We would also like you to spread the word about the meeting, and to try and get input from people outside the consortium
- If you can think of any potential topics you would like to present on, or know of anyone who would like to present please let me know at robert.dewar@apha.gov.uk

3. WP 3.5 Development of tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis

Rob Dewar (APHA) - Contact: Robert.Dewar@apha.gov.uk; Charlotte.Cook@apha.gov.uk

Work so far...

- Literature sourcing
- Literature refinement
- Literature categorisation
- 'Lego-brick' CBA characteristics breakdown

Initial findings

- Of the 50 papers, 13 talked exclusively about salmonella
- 9 talked exclusively about campylobacter
- These were the modal diseases
- 3 talked about toxoplasmosis and 4 talked about Echinococcus
- 5 talked about food-borne disease in general
- Methods of measuring cost and benefit included:
- Direct calculation of tangible financial costs, and subtraction from tangible financial benefits
- Ratio of tangible financial cost and benefit
- Repayment time
- Tangible cost/benefit calculation combined with quality of life metric eg: DALY/€
- As above but with quality of life conversion rate (to monetary value)

Plan for the future

- Aim to create a 'recipe book' for this sort of CBA
- Where each stage is provided a list of options that affect the 'flavour' of the overall mixture
- IE: A user can decide how to plan their CBA based on their situation

Feedback

- We would love to know if you know of any examples of Cost-Benefit frameworks for foodborne diseases!
- Please email us at: robert.dewar@apha.gov.uk; Catherine.McCarthy@apha.gov.uk

4. WP 2.2: Decision tool to support One Health Risk Assessment

Rob Dewar (APHA) - Contact: Robert.Dewar@apha.gov.uk; Charlotte.Cook@apha.gov.uk

Work so far

- Assembly of risk assessment resources
- Isolate different approaches
- Discern the key decision-making themes
- Use these themes to develop a decision tree
- Convert the decision tree in to an online tool

Plan for the future

- We have secured web-space on the OH EJP website
- Aim to publish the tool before the end of the year
- Also aim to submit a short communication about the tool before the end of the year
 - Written but not yet finalised

5. WP 2.1: Implementation guidelines for One Health Risk Analysis Structures

Kitty Maassen (RIVM) – Contact: kitty.maassen@rivm.nl

To do, doing, done

- Web designer is finishing the outline of the website
- Illustrators are finalizing drawings, banner and pictures
- Drag and drop application will be postponed
- Writing content > reviews > adjustments > reviews > adjustments
- Determine to which tools to refer
- Gather best practices, experiences etc.
- Refine Terms of Reference
 - ➔ Regular workshops and homework

6. WP 2.3: Pilots of implementation guidelines for One Health Risk Analysis Structures

Kitty Maassen (RIVM) - Contact: kitty.maassen@rivm.nl

The One Health system to map

- Focus on zoonotic food borne diseases
- Focus on the parts of the system that do signalling, risk analysis, risk management, feasibility assessment, and governance
- Set a hypothetical goal of the system:
 - Reduced zoonotic disease burden in Norway

Initial mapping done by the project group

- Map with actors and stakeholders in the OHS and how they are connected and interact
- Resource systems, resource units (members or products of the resource system) and governing units
- Where and how is a signal created and forwarded, and where and how is a control action created and forwarded in the system?

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- An iterative process
- Our drafts were discussed with a few colleagues from NIPH and NVI and revised
- The map is not final(!) but it has been very useful to learn more about the OHS, system-thinking, and who to invite to the workshop

Step 3: Systems mapping

- Workshop with key stakeholders
- Led by Simon Ruegg
- Drafting the current system > context of the goal
- Also building on relation, trust and gaining support
- All workshops are postponed due to COVID-19

7. General items of COHESIVE

Kitty Maassen (RIVM) - Contact: kitty.maassen@rivm.nl

- Extension until 30-6-2021
- Finances > Y3/Y4 budget
- 12M report
- Update Data Management Plan
- Symposium > volunteers for organization?